

COMMUNITY BASED STUDY TO EVALUATE THE REASONS FOR INAPPROPRIATE USE OF ANTIBIOTICS

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ABSTRACT

Antibiotic resistance is considered to have a dangerous impact over the human health. Overuse as well as the misuse of the antibiotics lead to antibiotic resistance. This study was intended to identify the awareness in the community regarding the use of antibiotics and to identify the reasons for the irrational use of antibiotics. A questionnaire based community survey was conducted from January to June 2021 at Dakshina Kannada district in Karnataka. 150 participants who fulfilled the study criteria were recruited. 'Knowledge of Antibiotics' subset from the WHO Questionnaire used for the Survey for antibiotic resistance was used for data collection. The study protocol was approved by the institution ethics board. The study population consisted of 105 females and 45 males. Participants between the age group of 35-44 years were the majority (31%). It was identified that 32% of the participants were using antibiotics without prescription. There was a lack of advice from the professionals regarding the use of antibiotics, which may have led to early termination without completing the course of treatment. It was identified that 81 (79.4%) participants had utilized advices from the pharmacist on using prescribed medications including how and when to take antibiotics, with before and after indication, etc. 20.5% did not receive any advices on the use of antibiotics. Self-treatment, using stocked antibiotics from previous prescription, procuring medicines from family and friends were identified to be the reasons for the irrational use of antibiotics in the community. 70% of them were unaware about completing the course of antibiotics when used for treatment. The lack of awareness also led to the use of antibiotics for non-bacterial infections. The study identified a lack of awareness in the community about the use of antibiotics. Improving awareness and understanding of antibiotics and their use plays a vital role in tackling the rapid emergence of antibiotic resistance.

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INTRODUCTION

The 'Golden Age' of antibiotic discovery was considered from the 1940s up to the 60s, initiated by the discovery of penicillin in 1928[1]. From then, there is an increase in the consumption of antibiotics globally in account of rising income and insurance benefits, along with the increased burden of infectious diseases. Studies reported a 36% increase in 71 countries between 2000 and 2010, with three quarter of it accounted from Brazil, China, India, Russia and South Africa[2].

Spellberg in his article said that the greatest risk for human health in the future years will be from antibiotic-resistant bacteria[3]. There is an increased mortality rate by the multi-drug resistant organisms than other susceptible bacteria[4]. The resistance of bacteria to antimicrobial agents are due to the changes in their chromosomal structure as well as by the exchange of genetic material through plasmids and transposons[5]. The transmission and acquisition of antibiotic resistance is common in hospital setups, especially in India due to lack of control over the use of antibiotics along with primitive infection control and sanitation procedures[6]. The misuse of the antibiotic drugs as well as its overuse are the major factors leading to increased rates of resistance[2]. Interventions to deal with this crisis includes disinfection of treatment areas, introduction of novel drug delivery systems, as well as strategies to preserve available antibiotics and to delay their resistance[3].

Irrational use of antibiotics are considered to be the major factor leading to resistance. This include an increased prescription of antibiotics, demand from the patients, as well as the lack of control in the availability of the drug to the public leading to over-the-counter access to the drugs[7, 8]. Identifying the irrational use of antibiotics is necessary for initiating early intervention strategies for preventing the crisis of antibiotic resistance. This must be done at the community level as there is no control over the accessibility, leading to an overuse and misuse of drugs. The aim of this study was to evaluate the reasons for irrational use of antibiotics. This will help in initiating further steps required to stop the irrational use of antibiotics as well as the issue of antibiotic resistance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We designed a questionnaire-based community survey to identify the reasons for inappropriate use of antibiotics. The study was conducted among the residence of Valachil and Puttur areas of Dakshina Kannada district in the state of Karnataka. The study was conducted for a period of 6 months, from January 2021 to June 2021. The study was limited for a sample of 150 based on the time schedule allotted for the project including other circumstances. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) Reference number: SIEC/SIMS & RC/2021/03/01. The inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study.

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individuals of 18 years or older Both male and female gender Individuals who took antibiotics at least once during this year. Individuals who willing to participate in the study voluntarily 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age less than 18 years. Critically ill patients. Individuals who did not take antibiotics at least once during this year

The data for the study was collected using 'Knowledge of Antibiotics' subset from the WHO Questionnaire[9], used for the Multi-Country Public Awareness Survey for antibiotic resistance. The participants who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study were identified. The WHO questionnaire was used to collect relevant data from the recruited participants. The demographic details of the participants were analysed using descriptive statistics. The numerical values were also expressed in percentage for better understanding. Microsoft Excel software was used for segregation and analysis of the data.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

The study identified 150 participants who were eligible according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. This included 105 females and 45 males, making a ratio of 7:3. The participants were classified into groups according to their age, which is depicted in Figure 1. Majority of the participants belongs to 35 to 44 years of age. There were only 5% of the respondents above 65 years of age. Of the 150 participants recruited, 26% had primary education, 38.7% had secondary education, 25.3% were graduates, 4.6% were postgraduates, and 0.6% had doctorate degree.

Figure 1. Classification of Participants according to Age Groups.

Use of Antibiotics

It was identified that 69 (46%) of the participants had taken antibiotics in the last month, 78 (52%) took in the last 6 months, and 3(2%) of them had taken in the current year. Only 102 (68%) individuals were prescribed for antibiotics from a doctor whereas the remaining 32% represents the irrational use of antibiotics. It was identified that 81 (79.4%) participants had utilized advices from the pharmacist on using prescribed medications including how and when to take antibiotics, with before and after indication, etc. 20.5% did not receive any advices on the use of antibiotics. Figure 2 illustrates the sources by which the participants procured the medicines. Majority of the participants procured antibiotics from the medical store, few from family and friends, as well as from the previous use.

Figure 2. Sources from which Participants procured Antibiotics.

The below table (Table 2) summarises the data collected from the participants using the questionnaire to evaluate the knowledge about antibiotics among them. It was observed that 70% of them were unaware about completing the course of antibiotics when used for treatment. Only 30% responded they believe that antibiotics should be taken as directed. 79% of them claimed the use of same antibiotics for their friends or family to treat the same illness. 66% of them considered it to be reasonable to demand the doctor for the same antibiotics as it helped previously for the same symptoms. It was identified that the participants had low knowledge regarding the use of antibiotics in various medical conditions. Majority of the participants believed that antibiotics could be used for non-bacterial infections like flu, HIV/AIDS, sore throat, etc.

Table 2. Knowledge about antibiotics among participants identified using WHO Questionnaire.

Sl. No		Respondents (%)
1	When do you think you should stop taking antibiotics once you've begun treatment?	
Ans.	When you feel better	70
	When you've taken all of the antibiotics directed	30
2	Is it okay to use antibiotics that were given to a friend or family member, as long as they were used to treat the same illness?	
Ans.	True	79.3
	False	20.7
3	It's okay to buy the same antibiotics, or request these from a doctor, if you're sick and they helped you to get better when you had the same symptoms.	
Ans.	True	66
	False	34
4	Do you think these conditions can be treated with antibiotics	
	HIV	6.7
	Cold and flu	52
	Fever	85.3
	Measles	10.7
	Body ache	32.7
	Bladder infection/ urinary tract infection	13.3
	Gonorrhoea	16
	Diarrhoea	12.7
	Malaria	14
	Headache	35.3
	Sore throat	22

Reasons for the irrational use of Antibiotics

The study identified that 32% of participants agreed they consume self-medication with regard to the use of antibiotics. 75% of the participants use antibiotics even for non-bacterial infections like cold and flu, sore throat, and body pain, and 70% of the participants don't complete the course of antibiotic treatment by either skipping doses or stopping antibiotics once they feel better. 28% of the participants save the antibiotics from the previous illness. 20.58% of participants are not receiving complete advice on how to take antibiotics (such as with food, for 7 days, etc.). 79.53% of participants borrow antibiotics from their friend or family when they feel it is required. Figure 3 depicts the reasons for the irrational use of antibiotics as identified by the study.

Figure 3. Reasons for the irrational use of antibiotics.

Antibiotic resistance is considered to be one of the major crisis in the field of human health, which requires high priority interventions. Our study identified an increased inappropriate use of antibiotics among the people living in the communities. 32% of the study population consumed antibiotics without the prescription of a medical practitioner. Only 75% of the population purchased the antibiotics from local pharmacy whereas other found other sources such as friends and family, as well as from previous stock. This may have also caused a consumption of expired drugs, but was not investigated in this study. 20.5% of them did not receive any advices regarding the appropriate use of drugs, which may have led to early termination of antibiotics without completing the course. According to the data collected from the study population, we identified the reasons for the irrational use of antibiotics, which were self-medication, use of antibiotics in non-bacterial infections like cold and flu, sore throat, body pain, not completing course of antibiotic treatment either by skipping doses or stopping antibiotics once they feel better, saving the antibiotics from their previous illness, not receiving complete advice on how to take antibiotics (e.g., with food, for 7 days, etc.), and borrowing antibiotics from their friends or family. Laxminarayan et al., pointed out that poor public health indicators, rising income, and the availability of inexpensive antibiotics without prescription are the key factors creating an ideal situation for the irrational use of antibiotics in India[7].

Machowska et al., identified the drivers for irrational use of antibiotics in Europe. The public related drivers were the lack of knowledge and awareness, access without prescription, and the left-over antibiotics from previous prescriptions, leading to self-medication. The healthcare provider related drivers were the attitude and perception of the professionals, lack of adequate education, pharmaceutical promotion, lack of diagnostic tests, and the issues in patient-doctor relationship[10].

The situation of antibiotic resistance not only creates medical consequences, but also lead to an increased cost of healthcare for the society via newer costly antibiotics, increase in manpower and resources for improving hospital care, etc. [6]. World Health Organization has proposed a global action plan on antimicrobial resistance with five main objectives; to improve awareness and understanding of antimicrobial resistance, to strengthen surveillance and research, to reduce the incidence of infection, to optimize the use of antimicrobial medicines, and to ensure sustainable investment in countering antimicrobial resistance[11].The studies also suggest the importance of education programmes for the professionals and the public, as well as in the implementation of regulatory bodies with central prescription and advertising restrictions for antibiotics[6].

The antibiotic stress in the environment is less with shorter duration of treatment. Identifying the pathogen and using target specific drugs rather than broad spectrum antibiotics will help in minimising the problem[8].Distribution of standard treatment guidelines, increase in the diagnostic tests, vaccinations to improve immunity, along with reducing and restricting the use of antibiotics in the veterinary and agriculture sector are considered to bring rationalization in the use of antibiotics in India[12].

We identified a lack of awareness in the community regarding the use of antibiotics and their after effects is one of the major reason for inappropriate use of antibiotics. This calls for an active intervention comprising of educational and awareness programmes to prevent the irrational use of antibiotics. There must be a regulatory body to prevent the over-the-counter ease access to antibiotics. The drugs must also not be delivered without a doctor's prescription[13].Pharmacists play a vital role in the policy and guideline making and their implementation [14].

CONCLUSION

The study identified a lack of awareness in the community about the use of antibiotics and reasons were self-medication, early termination and saving for later use, lack of advice from professionals, and the use of antibiotics in non-bacterial conditions. Improving awareness and understanding of antibiotics and their use plays a vital role in tackling the rapid emergence of antibiotic resistance.

Bottom Line – We suggest future research in this topic on larger population group, including all sectors of the community so as to tailor the further actions necessary to prevent the irrational use of antibiotics.

AUTHORS' STATEMENT

Acknowledgements

Nil

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest

REFERENCES

- Hutchings MI, Truman AW, Wilkinson B. Antibiotics: past, present and future. *Curr Opin Microbiol* 2019; 51: 72–80.
- Singh SK, Sengupta S, Antony R, et al. Variations in antibiotic use across India: multi-centre study through Global Point Prevalence survey. *J Hosp Infect* 2019; 103: 280–283.
- Spellberg B, Bartlett JG, Gilbert DN. The Future of Antibiotics and Resistance. *N Engl J Med* 2013; 368: 299–302.
- Munita JM, Arias CA. Mechanisms of Antibiotic Resistance. *Microbiol Spectr* 2016; 4: 119–127.
- Neu HC. The crisis in antibiotic resistance. *Science* 1992; 257: 106–1073.
- Raghunath D. Emerging antibiotic resistance in bacteria with special reference to India. *J Biosci* 2008; 33: 593–603.
- Laxminarayan R, Chaudhury RR. Antibiotic Resistance in India: Drivers and Opportunities for Action. *PLOS Med* 2016; 13: e1001974.
- Levy SB. The Challenge of Antibiotic Resistance. *Sci Am* 1998; 278: 46–53.
- World Health Organization. Antibiotic Resistance: Multi-Country Public Awareness Survey. 2015.
- Machowska A, Stålsby Lundborg C. Drivers of Irrational Use of Antibiotics in Europe. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2018; 16: 27.
- Antibiotic resistance. World Health Organization, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antibiotic-resistance> (2020).
- Ganguly NK, Arora NK, Chandy SJ, et al. Rationalizing antibiotic use to limit antibiotic resistance in India. *Indian J Med Res* 2011; 134: 281–94.
- Davies J, Davies D. Origins and Evolution of Antibiotic Resistance. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev* 2010; 74: 417–433.
- Maraghy D, ElMaraghy DA, Younis AM, et al. Survey on the irrational use of antibiotics among adults in Egyptian community. *Int J Pharmacol Pharm Sci* 2016; 3: 6–9.

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